

Beyond Sentiment Analysis with ChatGPT: Classifying Authors' Perspectives on Russian Topics

S1: ChatGPT prompt for positivity classification.

The goal is to identify whether authors of scientific abstracts are presenting Russia and Russian topics from a positive, neutral, or negative perspective:

A **positive perspective** emphasizes a favorable presentation of Russia or Russian topics under research with an optimistic tone. Examples of abstracts with a positive perspective are:

The pragmatic and imperialist frames have dominated the analyses of Russian foreign policy. Despite the glaring similarities of Russia's international conduct with expectations of pragmatism and expansionism, this study argues that Moscow's foreign policy has been informed by more nuanced and dynamic conceptions of international relations. To uncover the imagery of global politics, as conceived by Russia's top foreign policy makers, this study employs a critical geopolitics perspective. The latter views foreign policy as a social, cultural, discursive, and political practice of constructing, defending, and living the alternative claims about the 'truths' of international relations. The study illuminates Russia's spatial conceptions of the world, its views of the international actors, and its national identity discourse. It shows how this imagery enters Russia's geopolitical reasoning that provides the Russian government with 'rationality' for projecting soft and hard power in the neighborhood and beyond.

*This article investigates the role of the screenplay in early Russian cinema and the life and work of Aleksandr Voznesenskii, who is considered to be the first professional writer of screenplays in Russia. It is no coincidence that Voznesenskii, who had been a novelist, a poet, a playwright, a literary critic, a universal writer of the Russian Silver Age, was the first major Russian writer for the screen, since, in a country with a logocentric culture, film was closely connected with literature from its very beginnings. Voznesenskii's screenplays ('Tears', 'Silent Witnesses', 'The Queen of the Screen', etc.) had a major influence on the development of early Russian cinema and he had a productive creative relationship with Evgenii Bauer. His writings (particularly his theoretical essays of the 1910s and his 1924 book, *The Art of the Screen*) played a key role in the development of cinema studies in Russia. He polemicized with Lev Kuleshov in the post-Revolutionary debates about the relative merits of the 'Russian' and 'American' montage systems. Furthermore, Voznesenskii was one of the pioneers of Russian film education. He made increasingly doomed attempts to adapt to the new cultural models of the Soviet period. Yet the role and achievements of this exemplary and pivotal figure have so far drawn little scholarly attention. The article draws upon a wide range of archival materials.*

The transformation of Russian news agencies has not previously attracted much academic attention outside Russia, although it provides an interesting case for the study of state-media relations and the growth of digital media technologies. This article explores how TASS, as a state-owned news agency, has been able to retain its position

as a domestic and international provider of news in competition with other state- and privately owned agencies in Russia. It uses a case-study approach, employing in-depth elite interviews together with existing research, news sources, professional databases and marketing reports. The particular focus is on management issues and on the technological challenges affecting TASS' strategic actions and ongoing operations. We analyse (1) the historical development of TASS, (2) its role as a national and international agency, (3) its relations with the state and (4) its move to a B2C model. The article concludes that state financial support, combined with the strong managerial decisions taken by new executives, have restored TASS' strong position in Russia's highly competitive news market after the agency's significant decline in the 1990s and early 2000s.

A **neutral perspective** emphasizes a balanced and impartial presentation of Russia or Russian topics under research, with a focus on stating facts and describing data. Examples of abstracts with a neutral perspective are:

Vladimir Putin has made state-building a central goal of his presidency and recent scholarship has demonstrated that Russian formal institutions have indeed been deliberately reformed. Unlike studies that assess state-building vis-a-vis a particular outcome, our research examines what kind of state Russian political elites seek to build, and focuses on symbolic state-building strategies. To capture symbolic state-building in the Putin era, we examine the Pryamaya Liniya broadcasts: annual, high-profile TV broadcasts in which citizens pose questions to the president. We find that a broad range of formal institutions appear to be central to Putin's state-building project, a finding that runs counter to claims that governance is largely deinstitutionalized, informal and personal. We argue that symbolic state-building seeks to reconcile personalism and institutionalism, by conveying a dual image of a state in citizens' everyday lives - emphasizing both formal institutions, while also affirming Putin as the personal guarantor of the state's authority.

The article discusses a relatively obscure but significant aspect of work of the Russian and Soviet thinker Alexander Bogdanov-his science fiction novels. The author points out that, using the form of the utopian novel, Bogdanov has set forth his vision of the future society, in which not only Marxist ideas but also Bogdanov's own original concepts (such as bogostroitelstvo, lit. "God-Building," and Proletkult, i.e., proletarian culture) found expression. In addition, the author provides a brief survey of the history of the utopian genre in Russian literature. This genre is analyzed in the context of how the concepts of "justice" and "order" were understood in various works belonging to it, including Alexander Bogdanov's books.

In recent decades, the attention of researchers and policymakers has turned to state-owned enterprises (SOEs), in particular the role they play in science, technology and innovation and the methods they use to implement innovation strategies. In this paper, we look at Russian state-owned companies and their development plans, as well as the management tools they employ to forecast and prioritize technologies. Although most Russian SOEs rarely implement corporate foresight and technology roadmapping, certain successful cases are presented and discussed in the paper. Based on these case studies, we suggest a common structure of a technology roadmap that is suitable for SOEs.

This article discusses the methodology of developing tools for assessing regulatory factors and managerial impacts on the regional economy and individual sectors and businesses. The potential of projection models is investigated, including balance models, convergence of regional and sectoral projection and compiling reliable and representative data sets capable of describing the current economic situation. An attempt was made to develop a series of models for several regional economies; to that end, the modelling of managerial and regulatory impact assessment was used in combination with the well-known value chain approach. In the interests of effective public administration, one of the requirements is to create sectoral model formats compatible with the regional projection models. Results of pilot modelling managerial and regulatory impacts on Kaliningrad region's economies are presented through examples of agribusiness, transport, industry, tourism and recreation. Implementation of regulatory impact modelling in the framework of the suggested approach is proved for other regions. The main advantage of the developed models for the regional management is their ability to reduce uncertainty in decision-making due to obtaining estimates of the impact of the decisions on the changing situation and the conditions for the development of sectors and industries.

A negative perspective emphasizes an unfavorable presentation of Russia or Russian topics under research with a critical tone. Examples of abstracts with a negative perspective are:

Using data from fieldwork conducted in late 2009, this paper examines the Russian educational sphere and initiatives by the political elite to control and manipulate textbook content, testing objectives, and the structuring of curricula in order to maximize exposure to, and absorption of, its preferred narratives. Using a more detailed critical analysis of textbook content, I show that methods of discursive manipulation are used to highlight positive aspects of the Stalinist period - especially victory in World War II - while downplaying its political repression. This manipulation allows the state to both legitimize its version of Stalinist history and to perpetuate the underlying legitimizing function that version serves. In this way, the discourse implicitly justifies Putin's centralized state as the type of system that has historically produced great achievements for Russia. This article adds to the literature on the manipulation of educational content for political purposes generally, and in the case of Russia specifically.

Why do dictatorships favor harsher punishments than democracies? We use a rational choice approach to explain the stylized facts of Stalin's dictatorship-preference for harsh sanctions, higher incarceration rates, greater use of capital punishment, low tolerance for theft of state property and workplace violations. They are shown to be explained by the preferences of a rational dictator, who does not internalize the social and private cost of punishment.

Radical "Westernizing" transformations in extra-European countries, from Peter I's Russia to Meiji Japan, are traditionally presented as a response to pressures from the more militarily and technologically advanced European powers. This corresponds to the general tendency to view war as the driving force behind early modern state-building. However, the question remains: how exactly did such transformations happen, and what explains their timing? Why did some countries, such as Russia, embark on radical institutional restructuring that threatened large sections of the traditional military classes in the absence of any obvious existential threat, while in

others even clear and immediate dangers failed to ignite a full-scale "Westernization"? This article seeks to complicate the "bellicist" narrative of "Westernizing" transformations and to generalize about the role of elite conflict in propelling "self-strengthening" reforms. It argues that "Westernizations" in extra-European polities were enabled by breakdown of domestic political balance and driven by "challengers" emerging in the course of these conflicts, as they strove to maximize their power. Factional struggles accompanying "Westernizations" are interpreted here not as a conservative reaction against reforms, but as a process that preceded and enabled institutional restructuring.

For each abstract to follow, identify whether authors of scientific abstracts are presenting Russia and Russian topics on a positive, neutral, or negative perspective by only giving a number 1 to positive, 0 to neutral, and -1 to negative.

[BATCH OF 20 ABSTRACTS]

S2: ChatGPT prompt for sentiment classification.

Sentiment analysis of the following text. Give only a number 1 to positive, 0 to neutral, and -1 to negative without explanation.

[ABSTRACT]

S3: Positivity vs. Sentiment Classification.

Table S3.1. Comparison of positivity and sentiment classifications.

	GPT API positivity (N=13,938)	GPT API sentiment (N=13,938)
negative (-1)	4,768 (34.21%)	1,814 (13.01%)
neutral (0)	8,208 (58.89%)	11,306 (81.12%)
positive (1)	962 (6.90%)	818 (5.87%)